

Supplementary Table 1. Primer sequences for real-time quantitative PCR gene studies.

Gene	Primer sequence
<i>ABCB1</i>	Forward: 5'-GCCCTTGTTAGACAGCCTCA-3' Reverse: 5'-GGCTTTGTCCAGGGCTTCTT-3'
<i>ABCG2</i>	Forward: 5'-TGGAAATCCAGAACAGAGCTGGGGT-3' Reverse: 5'-AGAGTTCCACGGCTAAACACTGC-3'
<i>IL-6</i>	Forward: 5'-CCGCCCCACACAGACAG-3' Reverse: 5'-CCGTCGAGGATGTACCGAA-3'
<i>IL-8</i>	Forward: 5'-CTTGTCATTGCCAGCTGTGT-3' Reverse: 5'-TGACTGTGGAGTTTTGGCTG-3'
<i>ACTB</i>	Forward: 5'-AAACTACCTTCAACTCCATC-3' Reverse: 5'-ATGATCTTGATCTTCATTGT-3'
<i>GAPDH</i>	Forward: 5'-GAAGGTGAAGGTCGGAGTCAA-3' Reverse: 5'-GGAAGATGGTGATGGGATTC-3'
<i>TBP</i>	Forward: 5'-CACGAACCACGGCACTGAT-3' Reverse: 5'-GTTGGTGGGTGAGCACAAGG-3'

Supplementary Table 2. Chorioamnionitis stage and grade and Group B Streptococcus (GBS) diagnoses among preterm with chorioamnionitis, preterm without chorioamnionitis, and term pregnancies.

	Preterm Chorio (n=29)	Preterm (n=31)	Term (n=36)	p-value
Chorioamnionitis stage (n [%])	(n=19)	(n=24)	(n=22)	<0.0001
Stage 0	1 (5.26)	15 (62.5)	19 (86.4)	
Stage 1	7 (36.8)	8 (33.3)	2 (9.09)	
Stage 2	11 (57.89)	1 (4.17)	1 (4.55)	
Chorioamnionitis grade (n [%])	(n=19)	(n=24)	(n=22)	<0.0001
Stage 0	1 (5.26)	15 (62.5)	19 (86.4)	
Stage 1	7 (36.8)	8 (33.3)	2 (9.09)	
Stage 2	9 (47.4)	1 (4.17)	1 (4.55)	
Stage 3	1 (5.26)	0	0	
Missing	1 (5.26)	0	0	
GBS status (n [%])				0.05
Positive	5 (17.2)	2 (6.45)	5 (13.9)	
Negative	15 (51.7)	18 (58.1)	28 (77.8)	
Unknown	9 (31.0)	11 (35.5)	3 (8.33)	

Data are n (%) (Likelihood Ratio Chi Square test) for categorical variables. *p<0.05. Preterm Chorio = preterm with chorioamnionitis.

Supplementary Table 3. Effect of maternal prepregnancy BMI on mRNA expression levels of placental MDR transporter and inflammatory genes in preterm and term pregnancies.

Placental gene	Prepregnancy BMI				p-value
	UW (n=6-8)	NW (n=6-16)	OW (n=7-18)	OB (n=8-11)	
Preterm pregnancies					
ABCB1	1.14 (0.54, 1.32)	1.10 (0.59, 1.28)	0.91 (0.58, 1.21)	0.66 (0.59, 1.05)	0.64
ABCG2	0.62 ± 0.23	0.64 ± 0.19	0.67 ± 0.20	0.75 ± 0.19	0.45
IL-6	0.85 ± 0.29	0.82 ± 0.47	0.91 ± 0.36	0.96 ± 0.41	0.83
IL-8	0.18 (0.13, 0.84)	0.33 (0.14, 1.09)	0.55 (0.28, 0.84)	0.22 (0.15, 0.44)	0.23
Term pregnancies					
ABCB1	0.65 (0.34, 1.33)	0.67 (0.38, 1.01)	0.61 (0.34, 0.76)	0.75 (0.53, 1.81)	0.30
ABCG2	0.76 ± 0.34	0.78 ± 0.23	0.70 ± 0.33	0.78 ± 0.29	0.95
IL-6	1.31 ± 0.50	1.24 ± 0.41	0.97 ± 0.19	1.38 ± 0.44	0.26
IL-8	0.26 (0.23, 0.48)	0.22 (0.13, 0.62)	0.25 (0.14, 0.34)	0.64 (0.23, 0.82)	0.21

Data are means ± SD (ANOVA; normal distribution/equal variance) or median (IQR; Kruskal-Wallis/Wilcoxon test for non-parametric data). *p<0.05. UW = underweight. NW = normal weight. OW = overweight. OB = obese.

Supplementary Table 4. Effect of fetal sex on mRNA and protein expression levels of placental inflammatory genes and MDR transporters among preterm and term pregnancies.

Gene	Preterm			Term		
	Male (n=34)	Female (n=22)	p-value	Male (n=14)	Female (n=18)	p-value
<i>IL-6</i>	0.93 ± 0.39	0.76 ± 0.32	0.14	1.25 ± 0.32	1.10 ± 0.30	0.22
<i>IL-8</i>	0.32 (0.15, 0.79)	0.47 (0.18, 0.84)	0.99	0.40 (0.22, 0.62)	0.27 (0.16, 0.69)	0.57
<i>ABCB1</i>	0.98 ± 0.47	0.92 ± 0.36	0.62	0.65 (0.39, 0.94)	0.71 (0.38, 1.16)	0.79
<i>ABCG2</i>	0.64 ± 0.19	0.72 ± 0.21	0.17	0.65 ± 0.26	0.83 ± 0.29	0.10
Protein¹						
P-gp	3 (1, 4)	3 (1, 4)	0.64	1.5 (0, 4)	1 (0, 3)	0.76
BCRP	4 (4, 4)	4 (4, 4)	0.75	4 (3.75, 4)	4 (4, 4)	0.72

Data are means ± SD (ANOVA; normal distribution/equal variance) or median (IQR; Kruskal-Wallis/Wilcoxon test for non-parametric data). *p<0.05. ¹Immunolabeled area staining of the syncytiotrophoblast.